

CALL: HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01
TOPIC: HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01-01 - Services and tools to underpin a research assessment system that incentivises open science practices
PROJECT: GRASPOS: next Generation Research Assessment to Promote Open Science
PROJECT WEB SITE: HYPERLINK "<https://www.graspos.eu/>" <https://www.graspos.eu/>
GRANT NUMBER: 101095129

SCOPE OF THE POLICY BRIEF

This policy brief enables EU-funded projects contributing to the advancement of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) to report on progress and provide input for further policy analysis and development by the European Commission. This policy brief should be understood as complementary to the other mandatory reporting materials.

Policy background:

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is a flagship EU initiative to deepen Open Science practices across the [European Research Area](#) (ERA). As such it contributes to several actions of the [ERA policy agenda](#) (in particular ERA action 1 & 8). EOSC is also recognised in the [European strategy for data](#) as the data space for science, research and innovation which shall be fully articulated with the other sectoral data spaces defined in the strategy.

Overall progress is steered by the EOSC tripartite governance involving the Union represented by the European Commission, the participating countries represented in the EOSC Steering Board and the research community represented by the EOSC Association. The second phase of development of EOSC (2021-2030) takes place in the context of the EOSC European co-programmed Partnership, which brings together the European Commission and the EOSC Association.

The [EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda](#) (SRIA) co-developed with the entire EOSC community sets 3 General Objectives (GO), 14 Operational Objectives (OO) and 14 Action Areas (AA).

General Objectives (GO):

1. Open science becomes the 'new normal', by ensuring that open science practices and skills are rewarded and taught.
2. Researchers can seamlessly find, access, reuse and combine results, through the definition of common standards and the development of related tools and services.
3. A federated infrastructure under community governance enabling open sharing of scientific results is deployed and sustained.

Operational Objectives (OO):

1. Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025;
2. Make monitoring systems to gather data and evidence on best Open Science practices accessible through EOSC (including the development of a dashboard to monitor the evolving landscape of policies, infrastructures and open resources made accessible via EOSC by 2023);
3. Increasingly mainstream Open Science skills in European research-performing organisations (RPOs) including through the uptake of curricula and training frameworks related to data stewardship through the lifespan of the Partnership;
4. Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership;
5. Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming

interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing);

6. Provide the metrics and tools to measure the adoption of the FAIR principles for research artefacts and provide frameworks to help in certifying that repository services enable FAIR in EOSC throughout the lifespan of the Partnership;
7. Co-develop a first generation of a robust pan-European network of infrastructures for software source code (including incentives for the effective documentation and sharing of research software) by 2025;
8. Co-design and adopt a Rewards and Recognition framework for FAIR and open data practices in research during the lifespan of the Partnership.
9. Implement and evolve the EOSC Rules of Participation and onboarding process for EOSC providers and increase the number of service providers and services offered progressively over the course of the Partnership.
10. Deploy and operate an authentication and authorisation infrastructure (AAI) framework to manage user identity and access by 2024;
11. Implement the EOSC persistent identifier (PID) policy and architecture by 2025;
12. Co-develop a minimum metadata framework and provide a common search and access mechanism to EOSC resources across the EOSC federation by 2025;
13. Continuously monitor and promote the increased uptake of core services and EOSC resources, access to EOSC Exchange tools and services and ensure a feedback loop with the users;
14. Define models for availability and costing of services across borders by 2023.

Action Areas (AA) of a technical nature:

1. Identifiers
2. Metadata and ontologies
3. FAIR metrics and certification
4. Authentication / authorisation infrastructure
5. User environments
6. Resource provider environments
7. EOSC Interoperability Framework

Action Areas (AA) related to boundary conditions:

8. Rules of Participation
9. Landscape monitoring
10. Business models
11. Skills and training
12. Rewards and recognition
13. Communication
14. Widening to public and private sectors and going global

More information can be found from:

- https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en
- <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/open-science-cloud>
- <https://eosc.eu/eosc-about>

A) Overview of contributions in relation to the EOSC policy and EOSC SRIA objectives

The following tables offer an overview of the contributions of GraspOS to the EOSC policy and EOSC SRIA objectives.

Connection to General Objectives (GO):

GO1. Open science becomes the ‘new normal’, by ensuring that open science practices and skills are rewarded and taught.

One key objective of the GraspOS project is to facilitate and enable policy reforms in research assessment, fostering responsible assessment and enhancing recognition for the contributions of researchers and institutions in Open Science.

GO2. Researchers can seamlessly find, access, reuse and combine results, through the definition of common standards and the development of related tools and services.

While knowledge discovery is out of scope of the GraspOS project, it is anticipated that the project will contribute to the establishment of standards (e.g., API specifications) for sharing scholarly metadata that can be useful for the implementation of research assessment processes. These standards aim to streamline the development of pertinent services.

GO3. A federated infrastructure under community governance enabling open sharing of scientific results is deployed and sustained.

GraspOS aims to deliver an infrastructure designed based on a federated architecture (see also [D4.1](#)) that will aggregate open resources (e.g., metrics, indicators, data, tools, services) that can catalyse the implementation of policy reforms towards an Open-Science-aware and responsible research assessment framework, paving the way for the creation of an open research assessment dataspace.

Connection to Operational Objectives (OO):

OO1. Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025;

The work performed in GraspOS is relevant to various areas that relate to the Minimum Viable EOSC. For instance, the work around the area of “research data as a service” is of particular interest since GraspOS is expected to deliver an array of research data services offering open interfaces for stakeholders that would like to consume content from scholarly metadata sources for research assessment applications. Additionally, GraspOS is interested in the activities around the EOSC Interoperability Framework, especially those related to the “service management and access framework” and the “interoperability metadata framework”, since the project is expected to deliver end-user services as well as to increase the interoperability between sources of scholarly metadata and facilitate their consumption from added-value services. Finally, the area of EOSC around “monitoring, metrics, and accounting” is very interesting for GraspOS partners since the project is expected to deliver an array of monitoring services that are focusing on Open Science indicators and trends.

OO2. Make monitoring systems to gather data and evidence on best Open Science practices accessible through EOSC (including the development of a dashboard to monitor the evolving landscape of policies, infrastructures and open resources made accessible via EOSC by 2023);

<p>Among the others, GraspOS will deliver a set of monitoring services that can facilitate tracking research assessment indicators and the adoption of Open Science in different levels of granularity (e.g., researcher, organisation, country). One of the services being partly developed in the context of the project is the EOSC observatory.</p>
<p>OO3. Increasingly mainstream Open Science skills in European research-performing organisations (RPOs) including through the uptake of curricula and training frameworks related to data stewardship through the lifespan of the Partnership;</p>
<p>GraspOS is expected to provide comprehensive training materials and activities centered around Open Science and responsible research assessment (https://graspos.eu/training-material).</p>
<p>OO4. Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership;</p>
<p>GraspOS is positioned to make significant contributions to the establishment of services, practices, and standards in the realm of research assessment and the recognition of Open Science practices. The project has been structured to incorporate a diverse range of real-world pilots, each poised to provide invaluable feedback for the refinement and development of pertinent standards, services, and frameworks. Embracing a co-development approach, GraspOS is primed to harness insights from these pilots to shape and enhance its offerings in alignment with evolving needs and best practices.</p>
<p>OO5. Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing);</p>
<p>GraspOS is interested in FAIR assessment to ensure the quality of its scholarly metadata sources for research assessment use cases. The OpenAIRE Validator service, which is being extended in the context of the project, is a technical component of interest for the FAIR ecosystem. In addition, various GraspOS components offer community customisation features to be tailored for particular use cases.</p>
<p>OO6. Provide the metrics and tools to measure the adoption of the FAIR principles for research artefacts and provide frameworks to help in certifying that repository services enable FAIR in EO SC throughout the lifespan of the Partnership;</p>
<p>GraspOS incorporates and tailors FAIR metrics to enhance research assessment processes. Relevant tools, services, and recommendations developed in the context of the project can be of broad interest. Moreover, GraspOS is interested in FAIR assessment of its scholarly metadata sources.</p>
<p>OO7. Co-develop a first generation of a robust pan-European network of infrastructures for software source code (including incentives for the effective documentation and sharing of research software) by 2025;</p>
<p>GraspOS is not directly related to this objective.</p>
<p>OO8. Co-design and adopt a Rewards and Recognition framework for FAIR and open data practices in research during the lifespan of the Partnership;</p>
<p>A key objective of GraspOS is to incentivize a transformation in the existing research rewards and recognition system, ensuring that Open Science practices - encompassing FAIR and open data principles - are duly acknowledged and valued. In this context, the project will develop an Open-Science-aware responsible research assessment framework that will inform the tools and services to be developed in the context of the project. This framework will also consider the requirements from the diverse set of real-world pilots of the project following a co-design process.</p>

OO9. Implement and evolve the EOSC Rules of Participation and onboarding process for EOSC providers and increase the number of service providers and services offered progressively over the course of the Partnership;
The EOSC Rules of Participation and the EOSC onboarding process are of interest for GraspOS because the project aims to deliver an open infrastructure that will (eventually) allow additional providers to offer their resources in its federated ecosystem.
OO10. Deploy and operate an authentication and authorisation infrastructure (AAI) framework to manage user identity and access by 2024;
While GraspOS will exploit EOSC AAI service if needed, this objective is not directly relevant to the GraspOS project.
OO11. Implement the EOSC persistent identifier (PID) policy and architecture by 2025;
While GraspOS is using PIDs for its purposes, this objective is not directly relevant to the GraspOS project.
OO12. Co-develop a minimum metadata framework and provide a common search and access mechanism to EOSC resources across the EOSC federation by 2025;
Apart from the fact that GraspOS is putting effort into making its resources (datasets, tools, and services) discoverable in EOSC Marketplace, this objective is not directly relevant to the GraspOS project.
OO13. Continuously monitor and promote the increased uptake of core services and EOSC resources, access to EOSC Exchange tools and services and ensure a feedback loop with the users;
GraspOS monitoring services can offer useful insights towards the uptake of EOSC services and resources.
OO14. Define models for availability and costing of services across borders by 2023;
GraspOS will analyse the operational costs of its services and will investigate potential exploitation and sustainability pathways after the project completion.

Connection to Action Areas (AA):

AA1. Identifiers	While the GraspOS services, tools and data sources utilise PIDs for various research-related entities (such as publications, researchers, and organizations), actively contributing to this area falls outside the project's scope.
AA2. Metadata and ontologies	The implementation of the GraspOS infrastructure necessitates the development of standards for sharing scholarly metadata, which hold value in the context of Open-Science-aware and responsible research assessment. GraspOS will build upon existing well-established standards (such as the SKG-IF model), extending them appropriately for the needs of the project and sharing the results with relevant stakeholders, working groups, and EOSC-related projects and governance structures.
AA3. FAIR metrics and certification	GraspOS is interested in FAIR assessment to ensure the quality of its scholarly metadata sources for research assessment use cases. Moreover, GraspOS incorporates and tailors FAIR metrics to enhance research assessment processes. Relevant tools, services, and recommendations developed in the context of the project can be of broad interest (e.g., FAIR assessment tests from the OpenAIRE Validator). Finally, GraspOS plans to follow the latest FAIR assessment advancements through OSTrails, another EOSC-related project.
AA4. Authentication /	While the GraspOS services plan to take advantage of existing EOSC-related work for AAI (if needed), contributing to this area is out of the scope of the project.

authorisation infrastructure	
AA5. User environments	The GraspOS federated infrastructure offers user environments tailored for different use cases of research assessment. All GraspOS resources (data, tools, services, guidance) are easily discoverable because they offer EOSC-compatible metadata that will be included in the EOSC Marketplace.
AA6. Resource provider environments	GraspOS plans to deliver a federated infrastructure to facilitate Open-Science-aware and responsible research assessment (see also D4.1) that will aggregate open resources (e.g., metrics, indicators, data, tools, services) from various providers. Initially, this infrastructure will be populated with the resources provided by the partners of the project, but the plan is that eventually additional providers can enter the ecosystem to offer their resources.
AA7. EOSC Interoperability Framework	Enhancing interoperability among data sources pertinent to research assessment is in the focus of the project to facilitate the development of added-value services on top of the respective data assets. In that sense, GraspOS is expected to contribute relevant insights and outputs that can be of interest to be considered in the EOSC Interoperability Framework.
AA8. Rules of Participation	While GraspOS will make use, where possible, of the principles related to the EOSC Rules of Participation, contributing to this area is not in the focus of our project.
AA9. Landscape monitoring	Among the others, GraspOS will deliver a set of monitoring services that can facilitate tracking research assessment indicators and the adoption of Open Science in different levels of granularity. These services can provide valuable insights for monitoring the EOSC Landscape and assisting informed decisions.
AA10. Business models	GraspOS will investigate potential exploitation and sustainability pathways after the completion of the project.
AA11. Skills and training	Research assessment, a key focus of GraspOS, intertwines with the rewards and recognition system. GraspOS aims to facilitate recognition and rewards for diverse research activities and contributions, ensuring that Open Science principles are duly acknowledged. These efforts are expected to enhance the recognition of highly skilled and appropriately valued researchers. Moreover, GraspOS offers a range of training activities on topics related to research assessment.
AA12. Rewards and recognition	One key objective of the GraspOS project is to facilitate and enable policy reforms in research assessment, fostering responsible assessment and enhancing recognition for the contributions of researchers and institutions in Open Science. GraspOS is actively exploring the outputs of CoARA and is keen on fostering collaboration to build bridges between CoARA and EOSC.
AA13. Communication	As an EOSC-related project, GraspOS is always aligned with EOSC communication policies and contributes in the respective communication channels.
AA14. Widening to public and private sectors and going global	GraspOS is not expected to focus on that subject. However, its infrastructure, data, tools, and services can be used by public and private institutions.

B) Key contributions subject to wider dissemination by the European Commission

While the GraspOS project has only reached the one-third mark of its lifespan, there are some key contributions of the project that are ready for wider dissemination amongst the EOSC community. In the next paragraphs we outline the most significant of them.

Assessment. GraspOS is expected to deliver infrastructure, data, tools, services, and guidance to help towards a research assessment reform that considers Open Science. However, only early versions of the respective project deliverables are now available.

Data. GraspOS is expected to create or enrich a wide variety of open datasets, which can be useful in research assessment processes. The list of datasets to be produced in the context of the project can be found in [GraspOS' DMP](#) and more details for each dataset can be found in the respective entries of the [GraspOS data registry](#).

Infrastructure. GraspOS is expected to deliver an infrastructure to provide data, tools, services, and guidance to facilitate a research assessment reform that will take into serious consideration Open Science practices. Currently, an early version of the respective infrastructure is only provided (see also [D4.3](#)).

Publications. All GraspOS-related publications, which can be found in the [respective page of the GraspOS website](#), are relevant.

Services. GraspOS is building a wide array of services that can assist research assessment processes and Open Science monitoring. More details for each service can be found in the respective entries of the [GraspOS services catalogue](#).

Skills/training. GraspOS is committed to delivering a comprehensive array of training materials and activities focusing on Open Science and responsible research assessment. Notably, the project has already developed initial training activities, with detailed materials accessible [in the respective page of the project website](#). Furthermore, recordings from these training events are readily available on the OpenAIRE YouTube channel. Looking ahead, the training activities will revolve around the creation of a collaborative training course, developed in tandem with technology and infrastructure providers, and hosted on the OpenAIRE learning platform, OpenPlato.

Software. GraspOS is expected to deliver tools that can assist research assessment processes and Open Science monitoring. More details for each tool can be found in the respective entries of the [GraspOS tools catalogue](#).

C) Synergies with other stakeholders

In the first year of the project GraspOS partners actively participated in EOSC-related events, including high level conferences such as the EOSC Symposium. In addition, the project was represented in organisational meetings such as the EOSC General Assemblies.

In particular, GraspOS was involved in a panel discussion on EOSC contributions to research assessment along with EU-funded project OPUS at the EOSC Symposium 2023. In addition, a joint workshop on monitoring Open Science was held at the Open Science FAIR 2023, involving GraspOS, OPUS and PathOS projects. These collaborative efforts aim at facilitating knowledge exchange and fostering synergies between our respective projects, enabling us to explore common challenges and opportunities within the EOSC ecosystem.

Additionally, GraspOS is a member of the EOSC Association Working Group on Communication and Engagement for Horizon Europe projects. By engaging in this working group, we ensure that the project participates in shaping strategies for community involvement and stakeholder engagement, and that our project effectively contributes to the broader goals of the EOSC. In particular, GraspOS provided input for the Macro Roadmap for the implementation of EOSC and took part in the discussions before and after the EOSC Symposium 2023 and the EOSC Winter School 2024.

Finally, GraspOS has strong ties with CoARA, with members of the consortium being CoARA signees and playing important role in the coordination of CoARA working groups, such as the [“Towards Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment” WG](#) and the [“Multilingualism and language biases in research assessment” WG](#). In addition, in April 2024, GraspOS will participate in a workshop coordinated by

the European Commission (EC) aiming to align the EC's funded project with the EOSC-Association Task Forces and CoARA for the Research Assessment visions and infrastructures.

D) EOSC challenges and lessons learnt of a policy nature

As per our project plan, the development of GraspOS tools and services commenced last September, with the current phase prioritizing the preparation of the respective beta versions and the requisite infrastructure to support them. Full integration into the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) landscape is slated for a later stage in the project timeline (after M20 - August 2024). Consequently, until now, the need to use EOSC resources, that could help GraspOS partners encountering implementation challenges, remain relatively low.

In general, an important issue identified is that the landscape of EOSC-related projects is huge and complex, hence, collaboration with other projects is not always straight-forward. However, various activities from EOSC-A (e.g., face-to-face meetings for EOSC-related projects, regular technical & communication calls) have alleviated the problem to a significant extent. Furthermore, navigating the intricacies of the EOSC architecture and determining the optimal integration of GraspOS within this framework present considerable challenges. It appears that several sessions held during EOSC events offer valuable insights and resources to help address this critical requirement.

E) Link to other EU policy priorities (beyond EOSC)

The main contribution of GraspOS in EU policy priorities is relevant to the CoARA¹ initiative, which advocates for an inclusive approach to research assessment, recognizing diverse outputs, practices, and activities that enhance the quality and impact of research. GraspOS's assessment framework mirrors CoARA's vision and is poised to enrich it with novel ideas. Notably, GraspOS is expected to offer insights into research assessment infrastructures and multilingualism, crucial areas where it holds strong ties with CoARA. Members of the GraspOS consortium actively engage with CoARA, participating in key working groups like "[Towards Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment](#)" and "[Multilingualism and Language Biases in Research Assessment](#)". These collaborations position GraspOS to contribute significantly to CoARA's objectives and foster a more inclusive and effective research assessment ecosystem.

In terms of EU sectoral policies, GraspOS is poised to make substantial contributions to the domain of "Research and Innovation"² by incentivizing the adoption of Open Science practices and promoting heterogeneity and equity in research endeavors. By facilitating the recognition of a diverse spectrum of activities, GraspOS plays a pivotal role in fostering a fair and inclusive research landscape. Moreover, the project is anticipated to offer valuable insights and resources pertinent to "Statistics" policies, including guidance on research-related measurements and access to essential tools, services, and data for analysis. Additionally, GraspOS aims to provide indicators for calculating relevant metrics, thereby enriching statistical approaches within research contexts.

While GraspOS does not focus on sustainable development goals, the project activities can be relevant to at least some of them. Indicatively, GraspOS could contribute in the field of (a) "Quality education" (Goal 4) investigating the need for measures needed in the research assessment frameworks to foster the participation of individuals from developing countries in higher education scholarships, (b) "Gender equality" (Goal 5) investigating possible gender-related biases in research assessment and helping reduce them - taking into consideration during research assessment maternal leaves for indicators etc, (c) "Decent work and economic growth" (Goal 8) contributing in improving the work environment for researchers and academics, (d) "Industry, innovation, and infrastructure" (Goal 9) improving ways to acknowledge technical & research expertise to foster innovation, and (e) "Reduced inequalities" (Goal 10) ensure equal opportunities regardless the country of origin.

Finally, GraspOS is not directly contributing to advance any of the five EU Missions for Horizon Europe, however its mission to foster Open Science and acknowledge the full range of research activities, by principle facilitates the valuable research work that is being conducted in the respective fields.

¹ CoARA: <https://coara.eu/>

² EU Sectoral Policies: "Research & Innovation": https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/index_en

SUSTAINABILITY AND LEGACY (MAX 1P)

Not Applicable (this section should be filled only by projects in their final reporting period).

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